

SCALE Statistical Analysis Plan

As the primary objective of the SCALE (Scalable Clinical Annotation with Location Evidence) study, we statistically evaluate the diagnostic performance of models trained using different annotation strategies. The training data varies depending on the employed annotation strategy. Specifically, we compare an algorithm trained supervised on cases with manual annotations, to algorithms trained semisupervised on cases with manual annotations supplemented with additional cases annotated using AI-derived labels. The AI-derived annotations strategies we compare are the count-based Report-guided Pseudo Labels (1) method and the proposed location-based SCALE method. Model performance is evaluated using the PI-CAI Hidden Testing cohort (2) and the PROMIS cohort (3).

For training, the PI-CAI Public and Private Training dataset (2), the ProstateNet dataset (4), a dataset from University of California Los Angeles (UCLA) (5), and a dataset from the Antoni van Leeuwenhoek (AVL) hospital are used. The following datasets are used:

- Testing Dataset 1: the PI-CAI Hidden Testing cohort combined with the PROMIS cohort.
- Testing Dataset 2: the PI-CAI Hidden Testing cohort.
- Testing Dataset 3: the PROMIS cohort.
- Training Dataset 1: the PI-CAI Public and Private Training dataset with manual voxel-level annotations.
- Training Dataset 2: the PI-CAI Public and Private Training dataset with manual voxel-level annotations supplemented with cases from the PI-CAI Public and Private Training dataset, the ProstateNet dataset, the UCLA dataset, and the AVL dataset with AI-derived annotations using the count-based Report-guided Pseudo Labels (1) method.
- Training Dataset 3: the PI-CAI Public and Private Training dataset with manual voxel-level annotations supplemented with cases from the PI-CAI Public and Private Training dataset, the ProstateNet dataset, the UCLA dataset, and the AVL dataset with AI-derived annotations using the location-based SCALE method.

The following algorithms are trained:

- Algorithm 1: trained supervised using Training Dataset 1.
- Algorithm 2: trained semisupervised using Training Dataset 2.
- Algorithm 3: trained semisupervised using Training Dataset 3.

To place the algorithms in the current scientific field, they are compared against:

- Algorithm 4: the PI-CAI Ensemble Algorithm, as presented in (2), which is the ensemble of the top-five teams' algorithms.

Statistical tests are reserved for the primary outcomes only, in compliance with expert guidelines (6). To maintain the type I error rate while investigating multiple comparisons, all study objectives are prespecified in a hierarchical family and tested accordingly (7), as shown in Figure 1. The permutation test is used to determine the statistical significance level for each comparison. Multiplicity is corrected for at each stage using the Holm–Bonferroni method, considering a base alpha value of 0.05.

Comparisons in a hierarchical family are tested from top to bottom. After testing Family 4, the tree splits in three branches. A comparison is only tested if the null hypothesis in the block above it is rejected. For example, if the null hypotheses are rejected for 1-4, 5A and 5B, but that of 5C is not rejected, then we move on to testing 6A and 6B with a base alpha value of $0.05 \cdot \frac{2}{3}$ but do not test 6C. Similarly, if only 5A would be rejected, only 6A would be tested, with an alpha value of $0.05 \cdot \frac{1}{3}$. If the null hypotheses for 5A, 5B and 5C are all rejected, then we move on to testing 6A, 6B and 6C, where the significance threshold is once again adjusted considering a base alpha value of 0.05.

Figure 1: Flowchart illustrating the strategic plan to test the study objectives, while maintaining the type I error rate. AP = average precision. AUROC = area under the receiver operator characteristic curve.

Calculation of P Values

The P value for non-inferiority or superiority in the context of a permutation test can be calculated directly from the null distribution. The null distribution is constructed as follows: randomly permute the predictions between modalities (Algorithm A and B) for each case and calculate the test statistic; repeat permutations and calculation of the test statistic many times to generate a distribution under the null hypothesis. The P value for superiority or non-inferiority is then calculated as the proportion of permuted statistics that are equal to or more extreme than the observed test statistic plus non-inferiority margin:

$$p = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \mathbb{1}\{S_i \geq S_o + \delta\}$$

Where $\mathbb{1}\{S_i \geq S_o + \delta\}$ equals 1 if the test statistic (S_i) is equal to or higher than the observed test statistic (S_o) plus non-inferiority margin (δ) in iteration i of the permutation test, or 0 otherwise. N is the number of permutation test iterations (100,000). The non-inferiority margin δ is 0.05, following Saha et al. (2). The P value for superiority is calculated by setting the non-inferiority margin δ to zero.

References

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I, hereby, approve the statistical analysis plan above (dated 17 February 2025), as intended for analyzing the primary objective of the SCALE study.

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